

The political economy of the new developmentalism agenda: strategic choices and short- and long-term issues

Helder Lara Ferreira-Filho¹
Jefferson Souza Fraga²

Abstract

The political economy of New Developmentalism faces a range of challenges. Many criticisms concerning the difficulties in implementing the New Developmentalist programme stem from misunderstandings about the distinction between short- and medium-to-long-term development strategies. A central issue within this framework is the appropriate level of the exchange rate. Indeed, in the short term, exchange rate depreciation tends to generate inflationary pressures and may negatively affect economic growth. However, if the strategy succeeds, the expansion of the industrial sector – particularly its more technologically advanced segments – can foster productivity gains that, à la Kaldor, may translate into real wage increases in a more sustainable manner. Another controversial element is the notion of “fiscal populism,” as proposed by Bresser-Pereira. In this context, beyond the temporal dimension – where an initial stimulus may prove unsustainable over the medium term – other factors also warrant attention. Initial macroeconomic conditions appear to be critical: whether the economy is operating below or above potential output; whether the current account is balanced or facing adverse pressures; and whether inflation is above or below the central bank’s target. Furthermore, the composition of public expenditures is highly relevant, depending on the size of the fiscal multiplier on GDP. This article seeks to examine the political economy of the policy prescriptions associated with New Developmentalism, particularly in light of current macroeconomic conditions. The analysis focuses on the short- versus medium-term distinction, which appears crucial for the formulation of a coherent and sustainable development strategy.

Keywords: New Developmentalism; political economy; exchange rate policy; fiscal populism; short- and medium-term development strategy

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¹Helder Lara Ferreira-Filho holds a PhD in Economics from the University of Brasília, Brazil, and serves as a Legislative Counsel at Chamber of Deputies in Brasília, Brazil.

² Jefferson Souza Fraga holds a PhD in Economics from the Federal University of Minas Gerais, Brazil, and is a professor in the Department of Economics at the Federal University of Sergipe, Brazil.

Introduction

New Developmentalism (ND) has emerged as a significant theoretical framework since the early 2000s, offering a systematic response to the persistent quasi-stagnation observed in many middle-income countries, particularly in Latin America. It seeks to explain why these economies have largely failed to replicate the rapid, sustained growth trajectories characteristic of their East Asian counterparts. Drawing its intellectual lineage from Classical Developmentalism and Post-Keynesian Macroeconomics (Bresser-Pereira, 2020), ND offers a coherent macroeconomics of development alongside a sophisticated political economy analysis. This classical lineage is particularly rich in Latin America, rooted in the structuralist contributions of ECLAC (CEPAL) and its economists. This tradition was not uniform, encompassing a spectrum of views from Roberto Campos in his early phases to independent thinkers. Among the latter, Ignácio Rangel stands out as a key intellectual influence on Bresser-Pereira's own formation, noted for his unique approach within the developmentalist field. This complex ideological history, navigating the precise roles of the state and the market, has been meticulously mapped by scholars like Ricardo Bielschowsky (1988) and more recently by André Nassif (2025).

At its core, the ND framework posits that achieving international competitiveness for domestic firms requires the strategic management of two key macroeconomic prices: the interest rate and, most crucially, the exchange rate. A competitive and stable real exchange rate, complemented by low long-term interest rates, is considered a prerequisite for enabling firms to expand their scale of production, invest in technological upgrading, and thereby enhance productivity.

However, the policy prescriptions of ND harbor a central tension that is both an economic and a political challenge. The deliberate pursuit of a depreciated exchange rate, while essential for long-term industrial strategy, risks generating significant inflationary pressures and contracting real wages and aggregate demand in the short term. This raises a critical question of policy coordination: how can a government sustain a competitive exchange rate without necessitating contractionary high interest rates that would stifle the very investment the policy aims to promote? This dilemma is frequently misunderstood by critics, who often overlook the fundamental distinction between the short-term adjustment costs and the medium-to-long-term strategic goals of the ND program. Indeed, if the strategy succeeds, the initial costs are expected to be outweighed by the expansion of the industrial sector. This expansion, particularly in technologically advanced segments, can foster significant productivity gains that, in a Kaldorian fashion, allow for sustainable increases in real wages and living standards over time.

The political economy of ND is further complicated by the challenge of fiscal management. Bresser-Pereira identifies "fiscal populism" – the pursuit of expansionary fiscal policies that are unsustainable over the medium term, that is, recurring deficits

that lead to a possible explosive debt path – as a principal threat. Such policies can independently fuel inflation, forcing the central bank to raise interest rates and thereby derailing the strategic devaluation effort. Yet, the critique of fiscal policy within the ND framework extends beyond simple sustainability. The initial macroeconomic conditions are paramount: the viability and impact of a fiscal stimulus critically depend on whether the economy is operating below its potential, the state of the current account, and the prevailing inflation rate relative to the central bank's target. Furthermore, the composition of public expenditure is of high relevance, as the size of the fiscal multiplier – and thus the efficacy of the stimulus in promoting long-term development – varies substantially across different types of spending.

Ultimately, the transition from ND theory to practice is not merely a technical exercise but a profoundly political process, contingent on the balance of power between competing social coalitions. The success of a developmentalist agenda hinges on the ability of a "developmental class coalition," comprising interests aligned with productive investment and industrial dynamism. This article seeks to examine these multifaceted political-economic challenges inherent in the ND policy program. By focusing on the distinction between short- and medium-term dynamics, we analyze the viability of its core prescriptions concerning the exchange rate and fiscal policy, particularly in light of the complex trade-offs and initial conditions that policymakers face.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a brief review of the relevant literature. Section 3 offers a discussion of the exchange rate's role, its macroeconomic effects, and the associated political economy consequences. Section 4 analyzes the concept of "fiscal populism" and its threats to a developmental strategy. Section 5 presents our main conclusions.

Brief literature review of new developmentalism

Before digging into New Developmentalism (ND), it is essential to shortly describe its intellectual predecessor, Classical Developmentalism (CD), which serves as the key concept for understanding the period's economic debate. According to Bielschowsky (1988), CD is best understood as the ideology of transformation defined by an economic project centered on integral industrialization as the pathway to overcoming poverty. This project was foundationally skeptical of market spontaneity, suggesting instead that the State must actively plan this transformation. The State's role was comprehensive: it was to define sectoral expansion, orient financial resources, and undertake direct investments in areas where private initiative proved insufficient.

A defining characteristic of New Developmentalism (ND) is its methodological approach. In contrast to the hypothetical-deductive method of neoclassical economics, which builds models from abstract axioms, ND employs a historical-deductive method, as CD does. This approach, shared with classical political economy and Keynesian macroeconomics, seeks to derive models from the observation of historical regularities

and empirical tendencies, aiming for more modest but realistic representations of capitalist economies (Bresser-Pereira, 2020). It is thus a theory designed to understand and guide the economic development of nation-states as they compete within the framework of globalization (Bresser-Pereira, 2011).

The macroeconomic core of ND is built upon a critical assessment of the market's capacity to self-regulate key prices and accounts, leading to a set of distinct policy prescriptions that challenge both orthodox and traditional heterodox views. A foundational proposition is that markets are inherently incapable of maintaining the five key macroeconomic prices at their "right" or balanced levels (Bresser-Pereira, 2020). These prices are: the rate of profit, which must be satisfactory to induce investment; the rate of interest, which should be kept low; the exchange rate, which must be competitive; the wage rate, which should grow with productivity; and the rate of inflation, which must remain low and stable (Bresser-Pereira, 2019). The history of capitalism, from this perspective, is punctuated by crises stemming from the misalignment of these prices, most commonly an excessively high interest rate and an overvalued exchange rate, which depress the profit rate and destabilize the economy. Consequently, ND posits the necessity of a developmental state that actively manages these prices.

Perhaps the most radical tenet of ND is its critique of the "growth with foreign savings" strategy. The theory argues that middle-income countries should actively reject foreign finance as a means to accelerate growth. The conventional wisdom that current account deficits, financed by foreign capital, supplement domestic savings to boost investment is considered self-defeating (Bresser-Pereira, 2020b). According to ND, the capital inflows required to finance these deficits invariably lead to a chronic and cyclical overvaluation of the domestic currency. This appreciation artificially cheapens imports and increases real wages, stimulating consumption but simultaneously eroding the competitiveness of the tradable goods sector. The resulting fall in profitability discourages investment, meaning that foreign savings effectively substitute for, rather than add to, domestic savings. Therefore, ND prescribes a policy of maintaining a balanced current account or, when facing Dutch disease, running a surplus (Bresser-Pereira, 2020).

The main theoretical contribution of ND concerns the determination of the exchange rate. It proposes a specific theory for its formation, where the rate fluctuates around a fundamental value but exhibits a structural tendency toward cyclical and chronic overvaluation in developing countries. This is not mere random volatility but a predictable pattern with decisive consequences for the economy. This relative predictability allows for a fundamental rethinking of economic planning and the investment function.

ND extends the Keynesian investment function, which demonstrates that expected profits depend on aggregate demand, by incorporating the exchange rate as a decisive variable determining access to both domestic and external demand. When the

currency is expected to remain overvalued for long periods – as described in the model of cyclical and chronic overvaluation – firms base their projections on this lack of competitiveness and rationally refrain from investing in the tradable sector. This creates a powerful trap that inhibits structural change and long-term growth.

To counter this, the central policy objective is to maintain the real exchange rate at a competitive level, specifically at the "industrial equilibrium". This is defined as the rate that ensures profitability and competitiveness for firms operating with state-of-the-art technology. This level is conceptually distinct from, and generally more depreciated than, the "current account equilibrium," as it is explicitly designed to foster investment in productive diversification and prevent the premature deindustrialization caused by chronic overvaluation.

For commodity-exporting nations, achieving this industrial equilibrium requires neutralizing the Dutch disease – the phenomenon where an abundance of natural resources leads to a currency appreciation that harms the broader tradable industry. As Bresser-Pereira (2010) demonstrates, ND proposes active policies, such as variable export levies or the creation of sovereign wealth funds, to manage commodity revenues. These mechanisms aim to shift the exchange rate from the appreciated "current equilibrium" toward the "industrial equilibrium," thereby protecting and promoting manufacturing competitiveness.

ND is also highly critical of the practice of maintaining structurally high interest rates as a primary tool for inflation control. Bresser-Pereira (2012) argues that high interest rates attract speculative short-term capital inflows (the "carry trade"), which directly contribute to exchange rate appreciation and undermine industrial competitiveness. Furthermore, they increase the cost of servicing public debt, restricting the fiscal space for developmental policies. A sustained reduction in the policy interest rate is therefore considered essential for any stable, long-term growth strategy.

On fiscal policy, ND carves out a nuanced position that is equally critical of both orthodox austerity and what it terms "fiscal populism" (Bresser-Pereira, 2020). The theory advocates for intertemporal fiscal discipline to ensure public debt sustainability and create space for counter-cyclical policies. As Bresser-Pereira et al. (2014) emphasize, this responsible stance differs from austerity by recognizing public investment, particularly in infrastructure, as essential for growth. This allows for deficits compatible with a sustainable development strategy, preserving the state's investment capacity.

While intellectually influenced by Classical Developmentalism (CD), ND represents a significant theoretical and strategic departure tailored to middle-income countries in a globalized world. CD, formulated for primarily pre-industrial economies, centered its strategy on import substitution and was pessimistic about the ability of developing countries to export manufactured goods. This generalization, however, must be qualified. Thinkers such as Ignácio Rangel, recognized for his profound independent

thought within the classical school, were a notable exception. Rangel (1983) pioneered a critique of the standard ECLAC/Prebisch pessimism, arguing optimistically for Brazil's unique capacity to export manufactured goods, a position distinct from the prevailing import-substitution model (Ramos, 2024). In contrast, ND is designed for economies that have already industrialized and argues that they can and must compete by exporting manufactures, necessitating a competitive exchange rate over high protective tariffs (Bresser-Pereira, 2018).

This distinction is particularly sharp regarding fiscal policy. ND's explicit and repeated emphasis on fiscal discipline represents a strategic political maneuver to create distance from the legacy of "fiscal populism" that discredited earlier developmentalist projects in Latin America. This stance serves to preemptively disarm the orthodox argument that any form of state intervention inevitably culminates in fiscal ruin. It is therefore not just an economic principle but a crucial element in the ideological battle for policy legitimacy.

The practical implementation of this framework faces considerable obstacles, including internal distributive conflicts, resistance from commodity-exporting and financial sectors, and the need for sophisticated institutional management. Recent scholarship has thus focused on adapting these principles to contemporary challenges. This includes developing instruments to reconcile fiscal discipline with expanded public investment, as highlighted by Fonseca and Prates (2021) and Kregel (2020), and aligning industrial policy with new "missions," such as the green transition, which Mazzucato (2021) argues broadens the strategic role of the state in line with ND principles.

The exchange rates effects and political economy consequences

The real exchange rate (RER) is the essential of the New Developmentalist (ND) strategy and, simultaneously, its most contentious element. The framework's central thesis – that long-term development requires a competitive and stable RER – clashes with the empirical reality of most middle-income countries. In Brazil, for instance, the RER exhibits a chronic tendency toward appreciation, a pattern systematically identified as a primary obstacle to sustained industrialization (Bresser-Pereira, 2020). As illustrated in Graph 1, periods of a competitive RER are not the outcome of deliberate policy but are typically the volatile by-products of severe economic crises. The sharp depreciations witnessed during the emerging market turmoil in the previous years until 2002, the deep domestic recession of 2015, and the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 plainly demonstrate this issue. The subsequent periods of appreciation underscore a persistent cycle that this section seeks to deconstruct, first by outlining the strategic role of the RER in ND theory, and then by examining the structural and political forces that perpetuate its misalignment.

Graph 1 – Real effective exchange rate of Brazil (jan/1988 – apr/2025), jun/1994 = 100

Source: Central Bank of Brazil.

From a ND perspective, the RER is the critical macroeconomic price that enables technologically proficient domestic firms to access global demand, thus liberating their growth potential from the constraints of the domestic market (Bresser-Pereira, 2011). Maintaining a competitive RER is therefore considered a necessary, albeit not sufficient, condition for fostering the capital accumulation, structural change, and productivity growth essential for economic catch-up (Oreiro, 2020). The policy objective is to manage the RER towards an "industrial equilibrium" – a level that ensures profitability for firms operating with state-of-the-art technology. This level is conceptually distinct from, and generally more depreciated than, the "current account equilibrium", as it explicitly aims to neutralize structural disadvantages like the Dutch Disease. This logic is rooted in Kaldorian dynamics: a competitive RER stimulates export and investment demand, leading to higher capacity utilization and economies of scale, which in turn incentivize innovation and generate positive productivity spillovers across the economy.

However, this strategic objective is systematically thwarted by powerful structural forces that anchor the RER at an appreciated level. For commodity-exporting nations, the primary mechanism is the Dutch Disease, whereby abundant natural resource revenues generate an inflow of foreign currency that renders the manufacturing sector uncompetitive. This structural pressure is amplified by macroeconomic policy

choices within a context of open capital accounts. The orthodox reliance on high domestic interest rates to control inflation creates a significant positive differential with international rates, attracting large volumes of pro-cyclical, short-term speculative capital (the "carry trade"). These two forces – one structural, one policy-induced – conspire to generate a cycle of prolonged overvaluation, punctuated by abrupt, crisis-driven reversals when capital flows recede, in a dynamic famously characterized as "sudden stops" (Calvo, 2014; Bresser-Pereira, 2020b). The underdevelopment itself impedes the permanent state of appreciation of the currency, as the productive structure is not prepared to promote exports with higher value added. This can be seen as a trap, as the forces mentioned before tend to maintain the currency appreciated for a long time, inhibiting a real possibility of climbing the ladder of complexity in the productive structure.

This chronic misalignment is not a mere technical failure; it is the locus of a fierce political-economic struggle with clearly defined distributional consequences (Frieden & Stein, 2001). A strong currency creates a potent "appreciation coalition" – that is, a diverse set of social groups whose economic interests are served by an overvalued exchange rate – who are numerous and politically influential. This coalition includes wage-earners and consumers, whose real income and purchasing power rise in the short term; importers and the retail sector, whose profit margins expand; and factions of the financial sector. The mechanisms for financial sector gains are particularly powerful: they profit directly from the high-interest rates that often induce the appreciation (via 'carry trade' operations), benefit from the increased dollar-value of domestic assets, and see the local-currency burden of foreign-denominated liabilities reduced. Furthermore, this sector wields significant ideological power, shaping the policy debate by promoting a 'strong currency, strong country' narrative and possessing the ability to 'discipline' governments through the threat of capital mobility, thereby reinforcing the overvaluation bias. Conversely, the main proponents of a competitive RER are the producers of tradable goods – manufacturers and export-oriented agriculturalists – whose interests are often less concentrated and politically salient. The immediate, negative impact of a depreciation on real wages presents a formidable political obstacle (Oreiro & Marconi, 2016). ND resolves this apparent wage-led versus profit-led growth dichotomy by introducing a temporal dimension. While short-term growth may be stimulated by consumption, sustained long-term expansion is ultimately profit-led and constrained by the balance of payments. Without a competitive tradable sector, any growth spurt fueled by domestic demand will inevitably collide with an external deficit, as formalized by Thirlwall's Law (Thirlwall, 1979) and other studies after.

This underlying conflict gives rise to what ND theorists label "exchange rate populism". The political calculus is heavily skewed by a temporal mismatch between the costs and benefits of the RER level. The benefits of overvaluation – lower inflation and higher immediate consumption – are tangible, immediate, and widely distributed, generating broad political support. A typical historical landmark of this dynamic was

Brazil's Plano Real in the mid-1990s, which successfully used a sustained exchange rate anchor to end hyperinflation, thereby cementing vast political consensus around the 'appreciation coalition' for years. In contrast, its costs – deindustrialization, erosion of technological capabilities, and the weakening of the productive structure – are slow, cumulative, and less visible to the general populace. A politician who endorses or acquiesces to an overvalued currency can reap immediate electoral rewards, while the eventual balance-of-payments crisis is often inherited by a successor. This political asymmetry creates a powerful structural incentive for policymakers to favor short-term consumption booms fueled by an overvalued RER, even at the known expense of the nation's long-run development trajectory (Machado, 2024).

“Fiscal populism” and its threats to a new developmentalism strategy

A second formidable political-economic challenge to the New Developmentalist (ND) project is the persistent allure of fiscal populism, a tendency deeply rooted in Latin America's historically high levels of income inequality. In this environment, populist leaders can mobilize mass support by making sweeping promises of immediate material benefits, financing this largesse through unsustainable fiscal and monetary expansion. The New Developmentalist project is fundamentally incompatible with this model. It explicitly advocates for long-term fiscal responsibility – including control of public debt and the strictly counter-cyclical use of fiscal instruments – as a foundational principle to anchor the macroeconomic stability and predictability required for private investment. This disciplined stance arguably represents a crucial point of departure from past developmentalist experiments in the region, which were often undone by fiscal extravagance. The incompatibility is therefore profound: the instability, high inflation, and recurrent crises generated by populist cycles directly undermine the stable, low-interest-rate conditions that ND identifies as essential for structural transformation. Ultimately, the two models represent opposing temporal priorities: populism prioritizes the immediate distribution of existing income, whereas New Developmentalism prioritizes the creation of future income through sustained investment and structural change.

This theoretical stance stands in contrast to the model of economic populism, classically defined as a policy approach that prioritizes short-term growth and income redistribution while systematically downplaying the risks of inflation, deficit financing, and external constraints. This approach predictably unfolds in a boom-bust cycle. An initial phase of expansion, fueled by unsustainable government spending and wage increases, generates a temporary boom and widespread political support. This dynamic is powerfully illustrated by the period of Brazilian 'social-developmentalism' (roughly 2005-2014). This strategy, while formally maintaining the 'macroeconomic tripod' established in the late 1990s, ultimately relied on the "growth with foreign savings" model, financed by the global commodity boom driven by Chinese demand. As shown in Graph 2, the public sector's structural fiscal balance steadily deteriorated during this period, indicating a pro-cyclical fiscal expansion. This internal imbalance coincided

with a sharp deterioration in the current account (Graph 3), confirming that the economy was operating beyond its potential in an unsustainable, consumption-led boom. This cycle is exacerbated in Brazil by a high degree of budgetary rigidity, stemming from indexation and earmarking, which makes it exceedingly difficult to reverse populist-era spending increases during downturns. The result is often a suboptimal adjustment based on tax hikes and cuts to public investment – expenditures known to possess higher fiscal multipliers – thereby deepening recessions and hampering long-term growth (Deleidi et al., 2020; Fraga & Ferreira-Filho, 2023).

Graph 2 – Structural Fiscal Balance of the Public Sector of Brazil (1997 – 20243Q), % potential GDP

Source: Ministry of Finance of Brazil.

Graph 3 – Current Account of Brazil (1995 – 2024), % GDP

Source: Central Bank of Brazil.

These two forms of populism – fiscal and exchange rate – are not independent policy errors but are better understood as two integrated components of a single political strategy aimed at maximizing short-term, politically popular consumption. As Bresser-Pereira (2019) articulates, fiscal populism occurs when the state spends more than it collects, while exchange rate populism is when the nation as a whole spends more than it earns. The two are mutually reinforcing. A populist government first runs a large fiscal deficit to inject purchasing power into the economy. In an open economy, a significant portion of this new demand "leaks" abroad through imports. This leakage is facilitated and encouraged by an overvalued exchange rate, which makes imported consumer goods artificially cheap, thereby sustaining the consumption boom and masking inflationary pressures. Furthermore, the fiscal deficits often contribute to a higher inflation, compelling the central bank to maintain high interest rates, which in turn attracts capital inflows and further entrenches the currency overvaluation. The internal irresponsibility of the fiscal deficit is thus enabled and sustained by the external irresponsibility of the current account deficit, in a cycle that systematically prioritizes immediate consumption over medium-term investment.

This nuanced position places ND in a complex ideological terrain, subject to criticism from opposing flanks. On one side, neoliberal critics frequently conflate any form of state intervention with fiscal irresponsibility, employing "developmentalism" as

a pejorative term. On the other, some heterodox and post-Keynesian economists argue that ND's fiscal stance is overly orthodox and potentially contractionary, advocating instead for continuous fiscal stimulus to drive aggregate demand.

This critique is based on, for instance, the Sraffian-inspired 'supermultiplier' frameworks, which posit that autonomous demand – particularly sustained public investment – is the primary engine driving long-term growth and inducing private capital accumulation (Freitas; Serrano, 2015). From this perspective, ND's stringent focus on fiscal discipline appears unnecessarily restrictive, potentially sacrificing the main lever of development.

While the ND framework concurs on the importance of public investment, it's also considered open-economy constraints, which are often downplayed in demand-led growth models focused on closed economies or single-country assumptions. The core ND argument is that a sustained, fiscal-led expansion, if pursued before securing macroeconomic stability and a competitive exchange rate, is potentially self-defeating.

The mechanism is precise: in an open economy prone to structural inflation and external deficits, a large primary fiscal stimulus risks overheating and deteriorating the current account. This dynamic compels the central bank to maintain high policy interest rates to defend its inflation target and manage capital flows. These high rates, in turn, attract speculative capital, inducing the very currency appreciation that the entire ND strategy is designed to combat, thereby stifling the tradable sector's investment and profitability.

Therefore, ND's position is not an endorsement of austerity, but rather a strategic argument about policy sequencing. It postulates that fiscal discipline is the indispensable precondition to create the macroeconomic space (i.e., low interest rates) for the exchange-rate-led strategy to function and for private investment to flourish. The debate is thus reframed from a simple stimulus-versus-austerity dichotomy to one about the calibration and timing of fiscal policy in service of industrialization. A fiscal consolidation process may indeed have short-term contractionary effects, but these can be a necessary trade-off for achieving the medium-term price stability and external competitiveness that unlock sustained growth.

The importance of this framework becomes particularly salient when analyzing the current Brazilian conjuncture full of challenges (Ferreira-Filho and Fraga, 2024). Economic initial conditions are of paramount importance. By mid-2025, a consensus has formed that the economy is operating with a positive output gap: GDP growth has consistently surprised on the upside, the labor market is tight with unemployment at historic lows, real wages are rising above productivity, and inflation remains stubbornly above the central bank's target. In this context of overheating, the ND framework prescribes a clear counter-cyclical fiscal consolidation for the 2025-2026 period, implying a deliberate increase in the public sector's structural fiscal balance. Such a move would serve multiple strategic purposes. First, it would directly curb excess

aggregate demand, easing inflationary pressures. This, in turn, would allow the central bank to lower the policy interest rate, reducing the differential with international rates that fuels currency appreciation. Finally, the resulting RER depreciation would help correct the deteriorating current account deficit, realigning the economy's internal and external balances. Crucially, the potential negative short-term effect of this consolidation on output can be substantially mitigated by its composition. A well-designed fiscal adjustment that prioritizes cuts in low-multiplier expenditures (such as inefficient subsidies) while protecting, or even expanding, high-multiplier public investment can achieve the desired macroeconomic rebalancing at a minimal cost to short-run activity.

Conclusions

The political economy of implementing New Developmentalism, as dissected through the lenses of exchange rate management and fiscal populism, converges on a single, overarching challenge: the problem of time inconsistency. This paper has argued that the policies required for medium-term success under the ND model – most notably a competitive exchange rate and disciplined fiscal management – impose costs that are immediate, widely distributed, and politically painful. In contrast, the populist alternatives of an overvalued currency and fiscal profligacy provide benefits that are immediate, tangible, and politically rewarding, even as they sow the seeds of future crises and deindustrialization. Escaping this temporal trap is not a technical exercise but a paramount political challenge, requiring the construction of social and political institutions capable of insulating a national development project from the corrosive pressures of short-termism.

The solution, therefore, must be political. Overcoming these deeply entrenched obstacles hinges on the ability to forge a robust "developmental class coalition". As envisioned by ND theorists, such an alliance would unite key social groups – namely industrial entrepreneurs, workers in tradable sectors, and a meritocratic state bureaucracy – around a shared, long-term interest in industrialization and productive sophistication. The central task of this coalition is to negotiate the short-term wage-profit trade-off, convincing all parties to remain committed to the medium-term goals of enhanced productivity and sustainable growth in exchange for the future benefits of better-paying jobs and shared prosperity. This provides a direct answer to the critical question of how workers might be persuaded to support policies that could depress real wages in the immediate term.

However, this political coalition cannot succeed in a vacuum. Its endurance depends on the support of two complementary pillars: robust institutions and a compelling narrative. First, the project is critically dependent on a capable and autonomous state bureaucracy, in the tradition of the successful East Asian developmental states (Amsden, 1989). Key institutions such as development banks and planning agencies are essential for formulating and executing the long-term investment strategies that form the core of the ND agenda (Bresser-Pereira, 2019). Second, the

coalition must actively contest the ideological space. This requires a sophisticated communications effort to construct a positive "policy image" (Machado, 2024), reshaping the public narrative to dismantle the prevailing liberal consensus and demonstrate that a competitive exchange rate and disciplined public investment are the true pathways to innovation and sustainable prosperity.

The Brazilian conjuncture in mid-2025 offers a critical test for this framework. The current signs of an overheating economy – with inflation above target and a deteriorating current account – call for precisely the counter-cyclical fiscal consolidation that ND prescribes. A well-designed fiscal adjustment now could curb inflationary pressures, allow for a reduction in the policy interest rate, and facilitate a necessary depreciation of the real exchange rate. This moment represents an opportunity to pivot from short-term stabilization to the beginning of a coherent, long-term project, provided the adjustment is coupled with a qualitative shift in public spending towards high-multiplier investments in infrastructure and R&D. Ultimately, whether such a strategy can be initiated and sustained will depend less on its technical merits and more on the political capacity to build the developmental coalition, institutions, and public consensus needed to finally resolve the temporal dilemmas that have long constrained Brazil's development.

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